

ISic2734

I.Sicily inscription 2734

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

building; honorific
(?)

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

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Principal Contributor

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Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG7483

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333221

1. [— —]απ [— —] ²⁷[— —]αγ[— —](?) (Lazzarini)²⁷
2. [— — — —]
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644834

EDCS 64400333

PHI 333221

Bibliography

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